

Project-Based Learning in Engineering Education: A Systematic Review of the Literature

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Abstract

Project-based learning (PBL) has been widely recognized as an effective approach in engineering education, allowing students to apply theoretical concepts to real projects. This systematic review of the literature seeks to examine the benefits and challenges of PBL in engineering education, based on a systematic review of the literature. The methodology adopted included the careful selection of descriptors and databases, followed by a process of filtering and analysis of the articles obtained. Of the 43 articles selected, the results reveal a growing number of publications on the subject over the years, reflecting ABP's continued interest and relevance in engineering. The most relevant journals were identified, highlighting the transversality of PBL in the different areas of engineering. In addition, five key studies have been compiled that highlight the benefits of PBL, such as increased student engagement and the development of essential skills. However, challenges such as additional workload and complexity in the assessment have also been identified. Therefore, strategies to overcome these limitations are needed to maximize the benefits of PBL. A possible future direction would be the adoption of an Innovative Teaching Methodology that connects students to the job market, allowing them to apply their knowledge in real contexts under the supervision of professionals in the field. This approach would not only enrich the educational experience but also prepare students more effectively for professional challenges.

Keywords: engineering education, benefits and challenges, innovative teaching methodology.

1 Introduction

Project-based learning (PBL) has been recognized as an effective approach to teaching and learning in diverse educational contexts, including engineering education. PBL involves the exploration of theoretical concepts through practical application in real or simulated projects, allowing students to develop technical, cognitive, and socio-emotional skills that are essential for their professional training (OLIVEIRA; SEE; ROME, 2020). In the context of engineering education, PBL has been widely adopted as a strategy to engage students, promote meaningful learning, and prepare them for industry challenges.

This systematic review of the literature aims to examine the main benefits and challenges associated with the implementation of PBL in engineering education. To this end, a set of scientific articles that address this theme and present studies and experiences related to the application of PBL in engineering courses will be analyzed.

Articles published in scientific journals that address aspects such as the design and implementation of project-based courses, pedagogical strategies used and results will be considered. Information will be collected on the contexts in which PBL was applied, the types of projects developed, the assessment methods used and the results achieved in terms of student learning.

The methodology used for the selection of articles, data extraction and analysis of results is described below. The main findings of the review and their implications for educational practice are presented below. Finally, the limitations of the study will be discussed and possible directions for future research in the area of PBL in engineering education will be identified.

2 Method

The method used in this study was a systematic review of the literature, which involved nine steps based on the Methodi Ordinatio (Pagani *et al.*, 2022; Heathen; Kovalski; Resende, 2015). The measures adopted were as follows:

1) Stage - Establishment of search intent:

At this stage, the relevant descriptors were identified and the most appropriate combinations were made to answer the research question: "What are the main benefits and challenges associated with the implementation of PBL in engineering education?"

- Descriptors: Project-Based Learning - Engineering Education
- Time horizon: (between 2013 and 2023) - 10 years
- Peer-reviewed articles only.

2) Stage - Exploratory search with the descriptors in the databases:

The descriptors and combinations identified in step 1 were tested in the Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct, IEEE Xplore and ACM Digital Library databases.

Specific descriptors were used to search for articles, such as "Project-Based Learning" AND ("Engineering Education" OR "Engineering Education"), covering a 10-year time horizon, from 2013 to 2023. Additionally, we restrict our search to peer-reviewed articles, ensuring that only high-quality work is included.

3) Stage - Definition of the combination of descriptors and databases to be used:

The databases selected in Stage 2 were considered adequate, as they presented a significant number of relevant publications related to the descriptors researched, in addition to wide availability of access to the published materials.

4) Stage - Definitive search in the databases

The most representative databases in the international literature were selected for search, as described in Table 1, using the descriptors explained therein, over a period of ten years. The results of the searches in each database can also be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Database search results

TERMS	WEB OF SCIENCE	SCOPUS	DIRECT SCIENCE	IEEE XPLORE	ACM DIGITAL LIBRARY
"Project-Based Learning" AND ("Engineering Education" OR "Engineering Education").	30	244	444	174	253

From the total of 1145 articles found, and with the help of the Mendeley software, the following steps were taken.

5) Internship - Filtration Procedures

In the current stage, duplicate papers, papers presented at conferences that do not have an impact factor, books or book chapters, and those that did not adhere to the theme of the present study were eliminated, with the aim of further refining the selection of articles for analysis.

At this stage, the removal of duplicates was performed using the Mendeley software, which facilitated the efficient management of references. Then, we read the keywords and abstracts of each article in detail. Those that did not directly address engineering education were excluded, ensuring that only studies pertinent to the central theme were considered. This critical step ensured the inclusion of highly relevant literature for our analysis, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Filtering Procedures

Duplicate roles excluded:	264
Papers presented at conferences that do not have an impact factor, books or book chapters	545
Deletion of off-topic articles:	498
Total articles excluded:	779
Number of resulting articles in the portfolio:	47

Exclusion criteria included the elimination of publications such as conference papers, books, and book chapters, focusing exclusively on peer-reviewed journal articles. Adherence to the central theme was determined through careful analysis of abstracts and keywords, ensuring that each selected paper contributed significantly to the understanding of the benefits and challenges of Project-Based Learning in engineering education.

6) Stage - Identification of the impact factor, the year of publication and the number of citations

At this stage, the JCR of the journal where each of the articles was published was surveyed, as well as the number of citations of each one, in order to classify the articles, as proposed by the methodology used.

7) Stage - Classification of articles through InOrdinatio;

The classification of the articles was based on the calculation of the InOrdinatio of each article, based on the following equation (Pagani, Kovaleski, & Resende, 2015):

$$\text{InOrdinatio} = (F_i / 1000) + (\alpha^*(10 - (\text{ResearchYear} - \text{PubYear}))) + (\sum C_i)$$

Where: F_i = Journal impact factor;

α^* = coefficient attributed by the researcher to the relevance of the year of publication, which can range from 1 to 10;

AnoPesq – Year of search in the databases;

PubYear = year of publication of the article;

$\sum C_i$ = number of citations in the article.

In the survey, the value attributed to α was 10, considering that the timeliness of the articles is paramount.

8) Stage - Location of the articles in full

The location of the articles was done directly on the journal's website through the CAPES Journal Portal, with access to CAFe.

9) Stage - Reading and systematic analysis of the articles

After reading, four articles that did not contain elements to answer the research question were also excluded. To avoid saturation, the composition of the documentary corpus was limited to positive results in the InOrdinatio equation.

3 Findings

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the analyzed articles according to the year of publication, showing an increase in interest in the topic in the last five years.

Figure 1. Number of articles published on the topic over the years.

Figure 2 shows the most relevant journals on the topic of PBL in engineering education, considering the impact factor and the number of publications. The analysis of this graph allows us to identify the journals that are most dedicated to the topic, in addition to providing insights into the quality and scope of the research published.

Figure 2. Main journals of relevance.

The dispersion of journals in different areas of knowledge demonstrates the transversality of PBL, which can be applied in several areas of engineering. The presence of high-impact journals indicates that research on PBL in engineering education has been gaining recognition and quality. The relatively low number of publications in each journal suggests that PBL is still a developing research area with potential for future growth.

After reviewing the articles, the five main works were compiled that offer pertinent information for understanding the benefits and challenges of implementing PBL in engineering education. Table 3 summarizes the main characteristics of these studies.

Table 3. Main Articles on PBL in Engineering Education

ITEM NAME	AUTHORS	YEAR	GOAL	AREA OF APPLICATION	METHODOLOGY	FINDINGS
Additive Manufacturing: An Education Strategy for Engineering Students	A. Stern, Y. Rosenthal, N. Dresler, D. Ashkenazi	2019	Introduce an additive manufacturing course for engineering students	Engineering Education	Development of engineering projects using additive manufacturing	The engineering projects served as a useful learning experience, encouraging students' creativity and motivation
Proposal of a method of evaluation of individual contributions using the function point in the implementation phase in project-based learning software development	K. Tanabata, A. Hazeyama, Y. Yamada, K. Furukawa	2021	Propose a method of evaluation of individual contributions in the implementation phase in learning projects based on software development projects	Software Development Education	Using the Function Point Method to Evaluate Individual Contributions	Proposed method allows fair evaluation of individual contributions in software development projects
Combining Traditional Teaching Methods and PBL for Lean Manufacturing Teaching and Learning	G. Tortorella, P. Cauchick-Miguel	2018	Integrate traditional teaching methods and PBL into lean manufacturing teaching and learning	Lean Manufacturing Education	Traditional teaching approach combined with PBL	PBL can be an effective and complementary method for learning lean manufacturing
Applying project-based learning and SCAMPER teaching strategies in engineering education to explore the influence of creativity on cognition, personal motivation, and personality traits	T.T. Wu, Y.T. Wu	2020	Apply project-based learning and SCAMPER teaching strategies in engineering education to explore the influence of creativity on cognition, personal motivation, and personality traits	Engineering Education	Application of SCAMPER project-based teaching and learning strategies	Differences between students with high and low creativity in terms of cognition, personal motivation, and personality traits

4 Discussion

Table 4 shows the main benefits of using PBL, as discussed in the articles analyzed.

Table 4. Benefits of PBL in Engineering Education evidenced in the Articles.

BENEFIT	EVIDENCE IN THE ARTICLES
Increased student engagement	Stern et al. (2019): Engineering projects motivated and engaged students. Wu & Hyatt (2016): Active learning and student engagement in the construction of solar houses.
Development of Core Competencies	Stern et al. (2019): Engineering projects fostered creativity and problem-solving. Tanabata et al. (2021): Development of teamwork skills in software projects. Wu (2020): Influence of creativity on cognition, motivation, and personality.
Active and Contextualized Learning	Stern et al. (2019): Application of knowledge in real projects. Tortorella & Cauchick-Miguel (2018): PBL as a complementary method for learning lean manufacturing.
Better Preparation for the Job Market	Wu & Wu (2020): Developing skills relevant to the labour market.

In summary, the studies reported in table 4 suggest that PBL not only improves student learning, but also better prepares them for the job market and the real world (GONZALEZ, ALVARADO, PEÑA, 2017), promoting the development of essential skills and providing a more engaging and relevant learning experience. These findings highlight the importance of PBL as an effective pedagogical approach in engineering education.

PBL emerges as a dynamic educational approach, enabling the student to apply theoretical knowledge in real situations. This integration between theory and practice, as Fernandes (2017) points out, not only deepens the understanding of the concepts studied, but also cultivates essential skills for the professional world. In addition, by facing real challenges, students are led to explore creative and innovative solutions, stimulating not only critical thinking but also the ability to generate original ideas to solve complex problems, as highlighted by Gonzalez, Alvarado, and Peña (2017).

Collaborative interaction between students from different fields is another crucial facet of PBL, which promotes interdisciplinarity and the development of fundamental interpersonal skills. As Fernandes (2017) points out, this collaboration promotes the strengthening of teamwork, improves effective communication, and enables students to consider diverse perspectives, preparing them for the plurality of professional environments. In addition, by actively participating in the design and execution of challenging projects, students become protagonists of their own learning journey, which not only motivates and engages them, but also contributes significantly to their academic and personal development, as noted by Esteban and Arahal (2015).

Table 5 describes the main challenges cited by the articles analyzed

Table 5. Challenges of PBL in Engineering Education listed in the Articles

CHALLENGE	EVIDENCE IN THE ARTICLES
Additional workload for students and teachers	Stern et al. (2019): Engineering projects may require more time and effort from students.
Need for training and support	Stern et al. (2019): Teachers may need training to implement PBL.
Complex Valuation	Tanabata et al. (2021): Difficulty in evaluating individual contributions in software projects.

In this analysis, we will examine, according to table 5, the main PBLs, which summarize the challenges encountered in the implementation of PBL in different educational contexts. The goal is to better understand

these barriers and seek strategies to overcome them, aiming to maximize the benefits of this pedagogical approach.

Coordination and organization are significant challenges in the implementation of PBL, requiring careful structuring on the part of both teachers and students. Setting clear objectives, establishing development steps, and creating evaluation criteria are all essential steps for the success of projects. Additionally, it is critical to ensure that the necessary resources are readily available and that project teams are properly trained and monitored throughout the process, as highlighted by Cifrian *et al.* (2020).

Fair and objective evaluation represents another challenge in PBL, as highlighted by Colim *et al.* (2022). The analysis of projects in this context involves the consideration of various aspects, including individual student performance, team collaboration, and the results achieved. To address this challenge, it is essential to develop transparent and objective evaluation criteria, covering both the technical and non-technical aspects developed during the project. This approach promotes a comprehensive assessment that recognizes the complexity and diversity of skills acquired by learners throughout the project-based learning process.

5 Conclusion

PBL has been shown to be an effective pedagogical approach in engineering education, as indicated by the reviewed studies. The highlighted benefits underscore its importance in improving student learning and preparing for the job market by promoting engagement, skills development, and a more meaningful learning experience.

However, the implementation of PBL presents challenges, including additional workload, the need for teacher training, and complexity in assessment, especially in software projects. To overcome these limitations and advance research, it is important to investigate strategies to reduce workload, increase faculty support, and develop more effective assessment methods.

A possible future direction would be the adoption of an Innovative Teaching Methodology that connects students to the job market. This could be accomplished through a transdisciplinary project development lab, allowing students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts, under the supervision of professionals in the field. This approach would not only enrich the educational experience but also prepare students more effectively for professional challenges

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